

[David Berkowitz Chicago](#) is a famous USA painter. He finished elementary school in Aurora, and enrolled in [School of the Art Institute of Chicago](#), but he never completed the academy.

In 1969, during a football match, David Berkowitz Chicago suffered a serious injury on his spine and he was tied to the bed, and then started drawing for the first time.

David painted portraits of patients. Then he realized that painting was his passion.

In 1970, David became a member of the “Village”, but he distinguished from the other members of the group because of his style. He has sharpened his style by visiting a multitude of museums across the country.

David Berkowitz Chicago uses specific symbols in [his paintings](#), which distinguish him for the other painters of his group.

The most common symbols in David Berkowitz Chicago's paintings are water, pumpkin, as a symbol of wealth, farm, granary, and bareback horses. The element that gives unrestrained freedom in his paintings are the bareback horses.

David Berkowitz Chicago has presented his paintings to over 300 exhibitions over the world. His greater exhibition was in [the National Art Gallery](#).